

STRATEGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DISTANCE EDUCATION MODEL: PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS

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Abstract

The integration of schoolchildren into the field of ICT is considered one of the most important directions in solving the informatization problem of the modern school and increasing the level of professional training.

At the same time, the development and application of ICT is becoming one of the most important ways of increasing the efficiency of education in a modern school. Moreover, ICT as a factor in the social and economic development of modern society has a strategic role, because the technical means that provide them are both known and unquestionable.

Within the framework of the researched problem, three main approaches are used to understand the main concepts of the topic. The first approach is the technological approach. These basic concepts are information, information technology, computer and educational technology. The basis of these approaches is that ICT is a technical component.

The second approach is called the sociological approach. It is based on denying the synonymy of the main concepts of the sociological approach and some of the machines that underlie them. The main content of this approach is that people who make the most successful decisions in life are people who have connections with ICT.

Keywords: technical, humanitarian, approach, teacher.

The most important description of the main concepts of teaching, in terms of their inclusion in the educational process, is the humanitarian approach represented by its representatives: The humanitarian approach helps the teacher who teaches ICT in the practical implementation of theoretical constructions in the educational process. It should be noted that today there are no specific works on this approach related to ICT.

One of the most important problems in the study of this topic is the question of ICT classification, where it is possible to emphasize the diversity of approaches.

ICT is classified based on the following form of use in the learning process. This classification is based on the most promising forms of using information technologies in the educational process. Many researchers introduce the following forms: interactive teaching, electronic information resources and direct teacher-student communication in addition to existing teaching courses and topics (1).

The second classification is the data-based classification of data, texts, graphs, and real-world objects provided by the field of economics (2).

The third classification is distinguished by information processing technology - important concepts included in it: subject, provision and functional ICT (3).

Fourthly, we will express the classification of the developing ICT within the framework of the technological approach. This classification is based on the functional role of ICT. ICT itself is divided into three main categories - basic, primary and secondary (4).

The fifth one concerns the classification of the use of IT in distance education. Distance learning is a method of learning where the instructor does not need the instructor at a particular point in the learning process. This classification includes local and network ICT. (5).

This diversity speaks to the uncertainty of the views of researchers in the field of studying ICT in the educational process. In this regard, it is necessary to

adopt a classification (or some categories of classifications) that fully reflect the goals and tasks set by the teacher for the implementation of the training process.

Considering examples of ICT application in the learning process, it is mainly used in the following situations:

- organization of the educational process;
- preparation of teaching materials;
- research of new material (it is possible to choose two areas: independent presentation of the teacher and use of ready-made programs);
- computer control of students' knowledge;
- receiving and processing information from the Internet;

• creation and operation of a school website that allows students, parents and teachers to communicate (6).

For example, when learning new materials, two areas can be distinguished: the teacher's independent presentation and the use of ready-made programs.

The most superficial use of the computer is illustrative material. A computer screen (or a projector screen) is not about carrying a bunch of books, creating bookmarks, but also saves time, allows the teacher to prepare the necessary materials in advance, and also allows him to get audio materials that are convenient for him.

A lesson conducted with modern technologies becomes more productive and the teacher has the ability to teach more students than he can. The preparation of schemes and tables by computer is of special importance. This increases the pace of the lesson as much as possible and at the same time allows to eliminate the gap in learning the lesson.

Computer programs (Word, Excel, etc.) can help here. Currently, methods of conducting lessons with the help of computer programs are widespread. Therefore, the teacher's task is to identify the problematic issues and familiarize the students with the material in order to better understand the lesson. Sometimes, if it is not

required, it is not advisable to prepare a new material (although the use of ICT is well developed), as a rule, it is not practical, because the student is more burdened. In such situations, of course, it is possible to apply interactive methods that will allow the protection of attention. That is, a computer The use of er programs requires a lot of time for the teacher to conduct the lessons.

The main function of computer programs in the teaching process consists of a number of tasks that help students to take interest in lessons, increase learning motivation, repeat and generalize the material of the studied subject. The evaluation of the work done by the student is carried out based on the teacher checking the results or the completeness, accuracy, literacy of the answers and the efficiency of the teacher-student relationship.

Thus, the use of ICT in the field of education is applied in the sphere of educational environment created by the teacher and implemented by the student (mastery of knowledge).

It should also be noted that the variability of the listed opinions about the application of ICT in the educational process is more uneven in terms of the rapid development of the technologies themselves. Therefore, a distinctive feature of the development stage of the education system is the qualitative modernization of all its main components. Thus, intensive renewal of education is impossible without wide application of information technologies. The use of modern information

technologies in education is one of the priorities of development in the social sphere and is organically connected with the process of modernization of education.

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